

IMPACT OF THE NETWORK EFFECT ON PROFIT OR LOSS OF AIRLINES

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ABSTRACT

Airlines with a network, which includes short, medium and long-haul routes face different travel distances. The average trip length or average passenger haul is varying depending on the demand for longer or shorter travel distances. This variation leads us to the network effect.

We explore the network effect applying formal approach, and introduce the network effect coefficient in this paper. We set an equation for the break-even seat occupancy, which helps to calculate the number of revenue passengers at the break-even point.

Key words:

Network effect, break-even Load Factor, seat occupancy.

1. Average seat haul and average passenger haul

To arrive to the network effect formal expression let's introduce the following symbols:

- l_h Average seat-haul or average stage length (km)
- l_t Average passenger haul or average trip length (km)
- d_n Network effect coefficient
- P_r Traffic – Revenue Passenger Kilometres (RPK)
- P_a Capacity – Available Seat Kilometres (ASK)
- N_s Number of seats dispatched
- N_p Number of revenue passengers

Notice: Some airlines (e.g. Air Canada) apply miles in their Annual Reports, expressing the traffic in Revenue Passenger Miles (RPM) and the capacity in Available Seat Miles (ASM).

1.1. Average seat haul

Average seat-haul is the distance of hauling one aircraft seat (empty and occupied by a passenger) on the network.

We get the **average seat-haul** dividing total number of Available Seat Kilometres by the total number of seats dispatched:

$$l_h = \frac{P_a}{N_s} \quad (1)$$

From (1) the Capacity:

$$P_a = l_h N_s \quad (2)$$

Notice: Average seat haul equals average stage length; the proof is in (**Appendix 1**)

1.2. Average passenger haul or average trip length

By dividing the total number of Revenue Passenger Kilometres by the total number of revenue passengers carried we determine the average passenger haul or the average trip length.

$$l_t = \frac{P_r}{N_r} \quad (3)$$

From equation (3) the traffic:

$$P_r = l_t N_r \quad (4)$$

2. Seat occupancy and Passenger Load Factor

Seat occupancy or Seat Load Factor is the measure of seat capacity utilisation. The Passenger Load Factor (%) is the measure of capacity (ASK) utilization of an airline.

The Passenger Load Factor and the seat-occupancy on a single stage equal each other. The stage refers to a single flight between two airports, consequently, in this case, trip length equals stage length.

However, the Seat Factor and the Passenger Load Factor are usually different from each other on the network level. Behind this difference lies the difference between the average trip length and the average seat haul.

2.1. Seat-occupancy or Seat Load Factor (%)

Seat-occupancy (λ_s) is the quotient of the number of revenue passengers carried (N_r) and the number of seats dispatched (N_s). In other words: Seat Load Factor represents the **total number of seats sold** as a percentage of **total seat capacity** on all sectors (stages) flown.

$$\lambda_s = \frac{N_r}{N_s} \quad (5)$$

2.2. Passenger Load Factor (PLF) (%)

The Passenger Load Factor (λ) is the measure of capacity (ASK) utilization.

$$\lambda = \frac{P_r}{P_a} \quad (6)$$

The passenger Load Factor applying equations (2) and (4):

$$\lambda = \frac{l_t N_r}{l_h N_s} \quad (7)$$

The quotient of the average trip length and the seat haul we will refer as network effect coefficient (d_n).

$$d_n = \frac{l_t}{l_h} \quad (8)$$

In case if $d_n > 1$, the demand for travel distances longer than the average seat haul is prevailing over the demand for travel distances shorter than the average seat haul, and inversely if $d_n < 1$.

The shift of passengers to higher travel distances has a significant impact on the Profit or Loss (P/L) of the airline. An example of the impact of the network effect on an airline performance you find in **Appendix 2**.

Modifying (7) with (8):

$$\lambda = d_n \frac{N_r}{N_s} \quad (9)$$

Substituting (5) into (9), the Passenger Load Factor:

$$\lambda = d_n \lambda_s \quad (10)$$

PLF can be expressed as the product of the network effect coefficient and the seat occupancy.

In a specific case when the average trip length equals the average seat-haul ($d_n=1$) the Passenger Load Factor equals seat occupancy.

3. Break-even seat occupancy or break-even occupancy rate (%)

We can express the amount of the traffic (*RPK*) at the break-even point with the break-even Load Factor (λ_b), however, we do not know the number of revenue passengers at this point. Having the network effect coefficient, we can formulate the equation for break-even seat occupancy (λ_{bs}).

The revised Profit model (see **Appendix 3.**)

$E = P_a(\lambda y - c)$	(11)
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In (11) (*c*) is the unit cost (CASK – Cost per ASK) and (*y*) is the yield. The yield is the quotient of the passenger revenue and the traffic expressed in RPK.

Notice: RASK – (Revenue per ASK) is the product of the Load Factor and the yield in equation (11).

Substituting (10) into (11):

$$E = P_a(d_n \lambda_s y - c) \quad (12)$$

In case of break-even the Profit or Loss equals zero: $E=0$

From equation (11) the break-even Passenger Load Factor (λ_b):

$$\lambda_b = \frac{c}{y} \quad (13)$$

From equation (12) the break-even seat occupancy:

$$\lambda_{bs} = \frac{c}{d_n y} \text{ or } \lambda_{bs} = \frac{\lambda_b}{d_n} \quad (14)$$

The break-even seat occupancy (λ_{bs}) equals the break-even load factor (λ_b) if $d_n=1$, that is the average passenger-haul (trip length) equals the average seat-haul (stage length).

With the help of the break-even seat occupancy, we can calculate the number of revenue passengers (N_{rb}) at the break-even point:

$$\lambda_{bs} = \frac{N_{rb}}{N_s} \quad (15)$$

From (15):

$$N_{rb} = \lambda_{bs} N_s \quad (16)$$

An example of the calculation of the number of passengers at the break-even point you find in **Appendix 4**.

Summary and conclusions

I explored the phenomena of the airline network effect applying a formal approach. The shift of passengers to longer travel distances on the route network results in a longer average trip length over the average stage length. The difference between the average trip length and the average stage lengths explains the difference between the passenger Load Factor and the seat occupancy. We show how this shift of passengers to longer travel distances will result in additional Profit (**Appendix 2.**) compared to the even distribution case when average trip length equals average stage length.

I regard this paper as a contribution to the deeper understanding of the analysis of airline performance.

Appendix 5. contains the list of symbols applied in this paper.

REFERENCES

[Air Canada - AnnualReports.com](https://www.aircanada.com/en/pressroom/annual-reports)

Simon, Istvan - Airline's Key Performance Indicators

https://www.academia.edu/118469655/AIRLINES_KEY_PERFORMANCE_INDICATORS

Simon, István - Planning and Key Performance Indicators Practical Guide for Students 2021, Journal of Applied Business and Economics Volume 23(3)

Doganis Rigas - Flying Off Course Third Edition Publisher: Routledge 2002-10-20

APPENDIXES

Appendix 1. Average seat-haul equals average stage length (the proof)

Let's introduce the symbols:

- l_f Total distance flown per aircraft departures (km)
- N_d Number of departures
- l_s Average stage length (km)

Average stage length is the average distance flown per aircraft departure:

$$l_s = \frac{l_f}{N_d} \quad (17)$$

We can get the capacity by multiplying the average stage length by the number of seats available for sale.

$$P_a = l_s N_s \quad (18)$$

The capacity as in equation (2):

$$P_a = l_h N_s$$

Comparing equations (2) and (16) we find:

$$l_s N_s = l_h N_s \quad (19)$$

After reduction with the number of seats:

$$l_h = l_s \quad (20)$$

Appendix 2. The impact of the network effect (Air Canada case)

The figures of this **Appendix** based on the data gained from Air Canada Annual Reports 2014-2023.

FIGURE 1

The average trip length was significantly longer than the average stage length until 2019, then came the COVID-2019 pandemic

The difference in **miles** between the average trip length and the average stage length has small variance if we disregard of the pandemic years (yellow colour):

Years									
2 014	2 015	2 016	2 017	2 018	2 019	2 020	2 021	2 022	2 023
Miles									
102	97	82	67	76	81	34	13	85	83

The increase of difference between the average trip length and the average stage length in 2022 means the return of passengers to long-haul routes.

FIGURE 2

The clear indication of the network effect is the higher Passenger Load Factor in comparison to the seat occupancy

The Passenger Load Factor and the seat-occupancy run almost parallelly until 2019. Due to the suspended long-haul flights, the shift of passengers to longer trip lengths was limited, and the network effect started to weaken from 2019. The Passenger Load Factor and the seat-occupancy are almost equal in the pandemic years of 2020 and 2021. We saw the speedy recovery from the pandemic in 2022.

And finally, as a result of the network effect formalization, we can show (Figure 3.) how the shift of passengers to the travel distances longer than the average stage length effects the Profit or Loss of the airline.

FIGURE 3

The dotted line represents the case if the average trip length equalled the average stage length

During the pandemic (2019-2021), the shift of passengers to longer trip lengths was limited, and the additional Profit (generated by the network effect) started to decrease from 2019. The network effect practically disappeared in 2020 and 2021, when the company experienced a significant Loss. We saw the speedy recovery from the pandemic in 2022.

Appendix 3. The revised Profit model

The basic airline Profit equation as it is widely referred in relevant literature:

$$\text{Operating Profit} = (\text{Revenue}) - (\text{Operating Costs}) = \text{RPK} \times \text{Yield} - \text{ASK} \times \text{Unit Cost}$$

This equation is intended to focus on Profit however it provides an incomplete understanding of the relationship between the Profit drivers such as yield, unit cost and Load Factor. Our revised profit model is focusing on passenger transportation.

To modify the widely referred basic airline Profit equation we will apply the following symbols:

P_a Capacity – Available Seat Kilometres (ASK)

P_r Traffic – Revenue Passenger Kilometres (RPK)

- R Passenger revenue
- C Operating costs
- E Economic result (operating Profit or Loss)
- λ Passenger Load Factor (%)
- y Yield – total passenger revenue per RPK
- c Unit cost – total operating costs per ASK

Steps:

1. Operating Profit or Loss (P/L):

$$E = R - C \quad (21)$$

2. The yield:

$$y = \frac{R}{P_r} \rightarrow R = yP_r \quad (22)$$

3. The unit cost (CASK):

$$c = \frac{C}{P_a} \rightarrow C = cP_a \quad (23)$$

4. E again:

$$E = y P_r - c P_a \quad (24)$$

5. Introducing the Load Factor:

$$\lambda = \frac{P_r}{P_a} \rightarrow P_r = \lambda P_a \quad (25)$$

6. The economic result once again:

$$E = y \lambda P_a - c P_a \quad (26)$$

7. Finally, the revised Profit model:

$E = P_a(\lambda y - c)$	(27)
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The model (27) links financials (Profit - revenue - cost) and operational metrics (capacity – traffic – Passenger Load Factor) in a formal way. The interplay between the Profit drivers such as yield, unit cost and Load Factor, is clearly seen in this model.

Appendix 4. Calculation of the number of passengers at the break-even point

To validate mathematical models requires data. The main obstacle of validation is that for many figures is impossible to obtain publicly available data. Validation of mathematical models (14) and (27) for airlines having activities other than passenger transportation, can be done approximately only. The reason is that some cost elements, (e.g. IT, communication, etc.), relate to all kind of activities, not only to passenger transportation.

In case of airlines having passenger transportation activity only, the total costs relate to the passenger transportation itself and the validation can be performed.

In Air Canada 2023 Annual Report adjusted CASM is reconciled to GAAP operating expense and the calculated unit cost (CASM) is applicable for passenger transportation verification with good proximation. Abbreviation GAAP stands for Generally Accepted Accounting Principles.

We performed calculations based on the following data derived from Air Canada 2023 Annual Report.

Total operating expenses GAAP (CAD)	19 554 000 000
Passenger Load Factor	86,66%
Seat occupancy rate	82,90%
Revenue passengers carried	44 790 000
Passenger revenue per RPM (Yield) (cents)	22,61
Network effect coefficient (trip length per stage length)	1,05

Applying equations of chapter 3. we calculate the break-even seat occupancy and the number of revenue passengers at the break-even point for **passenger transportation** with cost of fuel and without of it.

Item	Excluding fuel	Including fuel
Operating expenses (CAD)	13 359 000 000	18 677 000 000
Unit cost CASM (cents)	13,49	18,86
Break-even PLF	59,66%	83,42%
Break-even seat occupancy	57,08%	79,80%
Number of revenue passengers at break-even point in 2023	30 837 995	43 114 097

Appendix 5. List of symbols

No	Designation	Measure	Symbols
1.	Average seat-haul	(km) or (miles)	l_h
2.	Average stage length	(km) or (miles)	l_s
3.	Average trip length or average passenger-haul	(km) or (miles)	l_t
4.	Break-even Load Factor	(%)	λ_b
5.	Break-even seat occupancy	(%)	λ_{bs}
6.	Capacity	Available Seat Kilometres or Miles (ASK) or ASM	P_a
7.	Economic result (Profit or Loss)	(USD) or (CAD)	E
8.	Kilometres flown	(km) or (miles)	l_f
9.	Network effect coefficient		d_n
10.	Number of departures		N_d
11.	Number of revenue passengers	(PAX)	N_r
12.	Number of seats dispatched	(Seats)	N_s
13.	Number of revenue passengers at break even		N_{rb}
14.	Operating costs	(USD) or (CAD)	C
15.	Passenger Load Factor	(%)	λ
16.	Passenger revenue	(USD) or (CAD)	R
17.	Seat occupancy	(%)	λ_s
18.	Traffic	Revenue Passenger Kilometres or Miles (RPK) or RPM	P_r

19.	Unit cost CASK or CASM	(¢/ASK) or (¢/ASM)	<i>c</i>
20.	Yield	(¢/RPK) or (¢/RPM)	<i>y</i>